

McCabe et al. 2021. Resource selection functions based on hierarchical generalized additive models provide new insights into individual animal variation and species distributions. *Ecography*: 44(10) p1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecog.06058>

Here we present two sets of monthly Eastern Golden Eagle relative probability of occurrence maps as .tif files. Please see the published manuscript for a description of the methods. The first set, labeled by *month*, is the raw output, while the second, labeled as *month.bin* represents the binned relative probability of occurrence values. Because the values represent a relative probability the numbers values themselves are meaningless and should be labeled as low to high.

The projected coordinate reference system is Albers Conic Equal Area and datum is NAD83 ("+proj=aea +lat_1=29.5 +lat_2=45.5 +lat_0=37.5 +lon_0=-96 +x_0=0 +y_0=0 +ellps=GRS80 +datum=NAD83 +units=m +no_defs").

To create the maps presented in the manuscript, the raw values were stretched to improve the visual contrast - this will allow you to see the variation of the more common values without being swamped by the absolute max and min. Here we use the standard deviation stretch type which applies a linear stretch between the values defined by the standard deviation (n) value, set to 2.5 here.

For purposes where binned values are required, we supply binned maps using a standard deviation classification method. The standard deviation classification method shows how much the values vary from the mean. Class breaks are created with equal value ranges that are a proportion of the standard deviation at intervals of one-third using mean values and the standard deviations from the mean.

* Please cite the manuscript when using any of the maps presented here. If there are any questions please email Jennifer McCabe at mccabe.jennifer@peregrinefund.org